

On a boundary value problem for an odd-order equation with multiple characteristics

Kurbanov Odiljon Tuxtamuradovich - PhD (Phys. & Math.)

Tashkent State Economic University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

odiljonkurbanov69@gmail.com

(+99890)9312596

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Abstract. In this article the author studied one nonlinear boundary value problem for a third-order nonlinear equation with multiple characteristics in a curvilinear domain. The unique solvability to the problem was proven. The uniqueness of the solution to the boundary value problem was proven by the method of energy. To prove the existence of a solution to this problem, an auxiliary problem was considered, for which the Green function was constructed. By solving an auxiliary problem, the original problem was reduced to a system of Hammerstein integral equations. The solvability of the nonlinear system was established using the method of successive approximations.

Introduction

The following equation refers to poorly studied odd-order equations:

$$L(u) \equiv u_{xxx} - u_y = f(x, y, u, u_x, u_{xx}), \quad (MC)$$

which is called an equation with multiple characteristics (MC) [1].

The equation with multiple characteristics (MC) arises in various problems of physics and mechanics, making it of significant theoretical and applied interest.

The well-known Korteweg-de Vries equation (KdV)

$$u_y + uu_x + \beta u_{xxx} = 0 \quad (KdV)$$

which is the object of research by many authors and occupies an important place in the study of nonlinear wave propagation in weakly dispersive media [2-4].

The Korteweg–de Vries (*KdV*) equation describes the evolution of weakly nonlinear long-wavelength excitations in a medium with dispersion in the high-frequency domain. The KdV equation finds applications in diverse fields, such as fluid dynamics (e.g., modeling gravitational waves in shallow water and nonlinear Rossby waves), plasma physics (e.g., describing ion-acoustic waves), electrical engineering (e.g., analyzing nonlinear circuits), and even epidemiology (e.g., simulating the time evolution of infected individuals during an epidemic), etc. [2 – 4].

Statement of the problem

Problem A. It is required to determine in domain $D = \{(x, y): h_1(y) < x < h_2(y), 0 < y \leq 1\}$ function $u(x, y)$ that has the following properties:

1) $u(x, y) \in C^{3,1}_{x,y}(D) \cap C^{2,0}_{x,y}(\overline{D})$; that has the following properties

2) which is a regular solution to the following equation:

$$L(u) \equiv u_{xxx} - u_y = f(x, y, u(x, y), u_x) \quad (1)$$

in domain D ;

3) satisfying the following conditions

$$u(x, 0) = u_0(x), \quad h_1(0) \leq x \leq h_2(0), \quad (2)$$

$$u_{xx}(h_1(y), y) = g(u(h_1(y), y), y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (3)$$

$$u_x(h_1(y), y) = \varphi(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (4)$$

$$u(h_2(y), y) = \psi(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (5)$$

and matching conditions

$$g(u(h_1(0), 0), 0) = u_0''(h_1(0)), \quad \varphi(0) = u_0'(h_1(0)), \quad \psi(0) = u_0(h_2(0)).$$

Uniqueness of the solution

Theorem (Uniqueness of solution). Let $h_r(y) \in C^1[0;1], r = 1,2$ and for $g(u, y), f(x, y, u, u_x)$ be continuous functions of their arguments $0 \leq y \leq 1$ for any $|u| < \infty$, satisfying the following condition

$$|g(\tau_1, y) - g(\tau_2, y)| \leq l |\tau_1 - \tau_2|, \quad (6)$$

$$|f(x, y, u_1, u_{1x}) - f(x, y, u_2, u_{2x})| \leq L \{|u_1 - u_2| + |u_{1x} - u_{2x}|\}, \quad (7)$$

$$2l - L \leq 1 + h_1'(y), \quad (8)$$

$$0 < L \leq \frac{N}{3}, \quad (9)$$

where $l > 0, L > 0, N > 0$ some constants.

Then the solution to Problem A is unique.

Proof. Let there be two solutions to the considered problem, u_1 and u_2 . Consider their difference $w = u_1 - u_2$. With regard to w , we obtain the following problem:

$$\mathbf{L}(w) \equiv w_{xx} - w_y = f(x, y, u_1, u_{1x}) - f(x, y, u_2, u_{2x}) \quad (10)$$

$$w(x, 0) = 0, h_1(0) \leq x \leq h_2(0), \quad (20)$$

$$w_{xx}(h_1(y), y) = g(u_1(h_2(y), y), y) - g(u_2(h_2(y), y), y), 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (30)$$

$$w_x(h_1(y), y) = 0, 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (40)$$

$$w(h_2(y), y) = 0, 0 \leq y \leq 1. \quad (50)$$

Let us prove that $w(x, y) \equiv 0$.

Having integrated the following identity

$$v w \mathbf{L}(w) v w L(w) \equiv v w (w_{xx} - w_y) = v w (f(x, y, u_1, u_{1x}) - f(x, y, u_2, u_{2x})) \quad (10)$$

over domain D , where $v = \exp(-x - (N+1)y)$, taking into account boundary conditions (20) - (50), we introduce the following notation:

$$I = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 v w_x^2 \Big|_{x=h_2(y)} dy + \frac{1}{2} \int_{h_1(y)}^{h_2(y)} v w^2 \Big|_{y=1} dx + \frac{3}{2} \int_D v w_x dx dy \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

According to notation (11), alternatively we have

$$I = -\int_0^1 v w w_{xx} \Big|_{x=h_1(y)} dy - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 v_{xx} w^2 \Big|_{x=h_1(y)} dy - \frac{1}{2} \iint_D (v_{xxx} - v_y) w^2 dx dy - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 h_1'(y) v w^2 \Big|_{x=h_1(y)} dy =$$

$$= \iint_D (f(x, y, u_1, u_{1x}) - f(x, y, u_2, u_{2x})) w v dx dy .$$

With conditions (6) and (7), we have

$$I \leq \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 (2l - L - h_1'(y) - 1) w^2 v \Big|_{x=h_1(y)} dy + \frac{1}{2} \iint_D (3L - N) w^2 v dx dy . \quad (12)$$

When conditions (8), (9) are satisfied, we arrive at the following inequality $I \leq 0$. Hence, $I = 0$.

Then from (11) we obtain the following conditions:

$$\begin{cases} w_x(h_2(y), y) = 0, & 0 \leq y \leq 1, \\ w(x, 1) = 0, & h_1(1) \leq x \leq h_2(1), \\ w_x(x, y) = 0, & (x, y) \in D. \end{cases}$$

Hence, we have $w(x, y) = p(y)$, $(x, y) \in D$. Since $w(h_2(y), y) = 0$, $0 \leq y \leq 1$, then $p(y) \equiv 0$.

Due to continuity $w(x, y)$ in $\overline{D}$ we have $w(x, y) = 0$.

Existence of the solution

Before proceeding to the proof of the existence of a solution to Problem A, it is necessary to study the following auxiliary problem.

Problem B. It is required to determine in domain D a regular solution

$$u(x, y) \in C_{x,y}^{2n+1,1}(D) \cap C_{x,y}^{2n,0}(\overline{D})$$

to equation

$$L(u) \equiv u_{xxx} - u_y = f(x, y) \quad (1_1)$$

satisfying the following conditions

$$u(x, 0) = u_0(x), \quad h_1(0) \leq x \leq h_2(0), \quad (2)$$

$$u_{xx}(h_1(y), y) = \varphi_0(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (3_1)$$

$$u_x(h_1(y), y) = \varphi(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (4)$$

$$u(h_2(y), y) = \psi(y), 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (5)$$

Let us construct the Green function for problem B.

The following identity holds:

$$zL(q) - qM(z) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^2 (-1)^k \frac{\partial^k z}{\partial \xi^k} \frac{\partial^{2n-k} q}{\partial \xi^{2n-k}} \right\} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} (zq), \quad (13)$$

where $M \equiv -\frac{\partial^3}{\partial \xi^3} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta}$ is the operator conjugate to operator $L \equiv \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \xi^3} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta}$,

and $z(\xi, \eta)$ and $q(\xi, \eta)$ are rather smooth functions.

Integrating identity (13) over domain D, we obtain

$$\iint_D (zL(q) - qM(z)) d\xi d\eta = \int_{\Gamma} \left(\sum_{k=0}^2 (-1)^k \frac{\partial^k z}{\partial \xi^k} \frac{\partial^{2n-k} q}{\partial \xi^{2n-k}} \right) d\eta + (zq) d\xi. \quad (14)$$

Now, in formula (14), for functions q and z , we take functions $u(x, y)$ - any regular solution to equation $Lu = f(x, y)$ and $U(x, y; \xi, \eta)$ - fundamental solution to equation $Lu = 0$ ([1]).

As ε tends to zero and considering the following equality ([1])

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{h_1(y-\varepsilon)}^{h_2(y-\varepsilon)} U(x, y; \xi, y-\varepsilon) u(\xi, y-\varepsilon) d\xi = \pi u(x, y),$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \pi u(x, y) = & \int_0^y \sum_{k=0}^2 (-1)^k \frac{\partial^k U}{\partial \xi^k} \frac{\partial^{2n-k} u}{\partial \xi^{2n-k}} \Big|_{\xi=h_1(\eta)}^{\xi=h_2(\eta)} d\eta + \int_{h_1(0)}^{h_2(0)} U(x, y; \xi, 0) u(\xi, 0) d\xi + \\ & + \int_0^y h_2'(\eta) U u \Big|_{\xi=h_2(\eta)} d\eta - \int_0^y h_1'(\eta) U u \Big|_{\xi=h_1(\eta)} d\eta - \iint_D U(x, y; \xi, \eta) f(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Let now $w(x, y; \xi, \eta)$ be any regular solution to the following equation:

$$-v_{\xi\xi\xi} + v_\eta = 0, \quad (16)$$

and $u(x, y)$ is any regular solution to equation $Lu = f(x, y)$. Now, assuming in formula (14) that $z = W(x, y; \xi, \eta)$, $q = u$, we have

$$\iint_D W(x, y; \xi, \eta) f(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta = \int_0^y \sum_{k=0}^2 (-1)^k \frac{\partial^k W}{\partial \xi^k} \frac{\partial^{2n-k} u}{\partial \xi^{2n-k}} \Big|_{\xi=h_1(\eta)}^{\xi=h_2(\eta)} d\eta - \int_{h_1(\eta)}^{h_2(\eta)} (Wu) \Big|_{\eta=0}^{\eta=y} d\xi +$$

$$+ \int_0^y h_2'(\eta) Wu \Big|_{\xi=h_2(\eta)} d\eta - \int_0^y h_1'(\eta) Wu \Big|_{\xi=h_1(\eta)} d\eta. \quad (17)$$

From equalities (15) and (17), we find

$$\pi u(x, y) = \int_0^y \sum_{k=0}^2 (-1)^k \frac{\partial^k (U - W)}{\partial \xi^k} \frac{\partial^{2n-k} u}{\partial \xi^{2n-k}} \Big|_{\xi=h_1(\eta)}^{\xi=h_2(\eta)} d\eta + \int_{h_1(y)}^{h_2(y)} W(x, y; \xi, y) u(\xi, y) d\xi +$$

$$+ \int_{h_1(0)}^{h_2(0)} (U(x, y; \xi, 0) - W(x, y; \xi, 0)) u(\xi, 0) d\xi + \int_0^y h_2'(\eta) (U - W) u \Big|_{\xi=h_2(\eta)} d\eta -$$

$$- \int_0^y h_1'(\eta) (U - W) u \Big|_{\xi=h_1(\eta)} d\eta - \iint_D (U(x, y; \xi, \eta) - W(x, y; \xi, \eta)) f(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta. \quad (18)$$

If regular solution $W(x, y; \xi, \eta)$ to equation (16) satisfies the following conditions:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} W(x, y; \xi, \eta) \Big|_{\eta=y} &= 0, \\ (W_{\xi\xi} - h_1'(\eta)W) \Big|_{\xi=h_1(\eta)} &= (U_{\xi\xi} - h_1'(\eta)U) \Big|_{\xi=h_1(\eta)}, \\ W_{\xi} \Big|_{\xi=h_2(\eta)} &= U_{\xi} \Big|_{\xi=h_2(\eta)}, \\ W_{\xi\xi} \Big|_{\xi=h_2(\eta)} &= U_{\xi\xi} \Big|_{\xi=h_2(\eta)}, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (19)$$

then from formula (18) we obtain

$$u(x, y) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^y Gu_{\xi\xi} \Big|_{\xi=h_1(\eta)} d\eta + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^y G_{\xi} u_{\xi} \Big|_{\xi=h_1(\eta)} d\eta + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{h_1(0)}^{h_2(0)} Gu \Big|_{\eta=0} d\xi +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^y (G_{\xi\xi} + h_2'(\eta)G) u \Big|_{\xi=h_2(\eta)} d\eta - \frac{1}{\pi} \iint_D G(x, y; \xi, \eta) f(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta, \quad (20)$$

where $G(x, y; \xi, \eta) = U(x, y; \xi, \eta) - W(x, y; \xi, \eta)$ we call the Green function of problem B.

Formula (20) gives a solution to problem B.

Note that for function $G(x, y; \xi, \eta)$ the same estimates as for function $U(x, y; \xi, \eta)$ are true (see [1]).

Solution to problem (16), (19) is sought in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
W(x, y; \xi, \eta) &= \int_{\eta}^y U(h_2(\tau), \tau; \xi, \eta) \alpha_1(x, y, \tau) d\tau + \\
&+ \int_{\eta}^y V(h_2(\tau), \tau; \xi, \eta) \alpha_2(x, y, \tau) d\tau + \int_{\eta}^y U(h_1(\tau), \tau; \xi, \eta) \beta(x, y, \tau) d\tau .
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

If $\alpha_k(x, y, z) \in C^1(D)$, $\beta(x, y, z) \in C(D)$, $k = 1, 2$, then the problem (16),(19) is solvable.

Theorem. Let, along with the conditions of the uniqueness theorem, the following conditions be satisfied:

$$\begin{aligned}
u_0(x) &\in C^3[h_1(0; h_2(0))], \quad \varphi(y) \in C^1[0, 1], \quad \psi(y) \in C[0, 1], \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial y}(f(x, y, u, u_x)) &\in C(\bar{D}), \quad f(x, 0, u(x, 0), u_x(x, 0)) = 0,
\end{aligned}$$

and for $y \in [0; 1]$ for any $|\tau(y)| < \infty$ the following inequalities hold:

$$|g(\tau(y), y)| < N, \quad |g_y(\tau(y), y)| < N_1, \quad |g_\tau(\tau(y), y)| < N_2,$$

and $f(x, y, u) \in C(D)$ for $(x, y) \in D$ and for $|u| < \infty$

$$\begin{aligned}
|f(x, y, u, u_x)| &< M, \quad |f_x(x, y, u, u_x)| < M_1, \quad |f_y(x, y, u, u_x)| < M_2, \\
|f_u(x, y, u, u_x)| &< M_3, \quad |f_{u_x}(x, y, u, u_x)| < M_4.
\end{aligned}$$

Then the solution to problem (1) - (5) exists.

Proof. From (20), we find

$$\begin{aligned}
u(x, y) &= -\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^y G(x, y; h_1(\eta), \eta) g(\tau(\eta), \eta) d\eta + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^y G_\xi(x, y; h_1(\eta), \eta) \varphi(\eta) d\eta + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{h_1(0)}^{h_2(0)} G_\xi(x, y; \xi, 0) u_0(\xi) d\xi + \\
&+ \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^y G_{\xi\xi}(x, y; h_2(\eta), \eta) \psi(\eta) d\eta - \frac{1}{\pi} \iint_D G(x, y; \xi, \eta) f(\xi, \eta, u(\xi, \eta), u_\xi(\xi, \eta)) d\xi d\eta,
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

where $u(h_1(y), y) = \tau(y)$.

Passing to the limit for $x \rightarrow h_1(y)$ in (22), we obtain:

$$\tau(y) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^y G(h_1(y), y; h_2(\eta), \eta) g(\tau(\eta), \eta) d\eta - \frac{1}{\pi} \iint_D G(h_1(y), y; \xi, \eta) f(\xi, \eta, u(\xi, \eta), u_\xi(\xi, \eta)) d\xi d\eta + F(y), \tag{23}$$

System (22)-(23) is a system of nonlinear Hammerstein integral equations with respect to $u(x, y), \tau(y)$.

Let $f(x, y, u(x, y))$ as known funktion, then from (23) we will find funtion $\tau(y)$.

$$\tau(y) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^y G(h_1(y), y; h_1(\eta), \eta) g(\tau(\eta), \eta) d\eta + E(y). \quad (24)$$

It is nonlinear Hammerstein integral equation with $\tau(y)$.

Equation (24) can be solved by the method of successive approximations.

Let there exist numbers K and N such that

$$|E(y)| \leq K, |g(\tau(y), y)| \leq N, |\tau(y)| \leq K + 1. \quad (25)$$

Assuming that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \tau^{(0)}(y) &= E(y) \leq |E(y)| \leq K < K + 1, \\ \tau^{(n)}(y) &= E(y) + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^y G(h_1(y), y; h_2(\eta), \eta) g(\tau^{(n-1)}(\eta), \eta) d\eta. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (26)$$

Assuming $n = 1$ in equation (26) and using the estimate [1], we have

$$|\tau^{(1)}(y)| = K + CN \int_0^y (y - \eta)^{-1/3} d\eta = K + \frac{3}{2} CN y^{2/3}.$$

$$(x, y) \in \overline{D}$$

In order for the value of the argument $\tau(y)$ of the function $g(\tau(y), y)$ to satisfy inequality (25), under which f is limited, it is necessary to fulfill the conditions

$$K + \frac{3}{2}CNy^{\frac{2}{3}} < K + 1, \quad \text{or} \quad y < \left(\frac{2}{3CN}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}. \quad (27)$$

For $n = 2$ from (26) we find

$$|\tau^{(2)}(y)| \leq K + \frac{3}{2}CNy^{\frac{2}{3}}.$$

According to (27)

$$|\tau^{(2)}(y)| \leq K + 1.$$

that is, when repeating (in the second) approximation of the argument $\tau(y)$, the function $g(\tau(y), y)$ does not leave the limited region (25).

Applying the complete method of induction, we conclude that none of the successive approximations will leave the region (25) if condition (27) are met.

Now, we will show that the limit of the sequence $\{\tau^{(n)}(y)\}$ exist.

To establish this, it suffices to prove the convergence of the series

$$\tau^{(0)}(y) + (\tau^{(1)}(y) - \tau^{(0)}(y)) + (\tau^{(2)}(y) - \tau^{(1)}(y)) + \dots + (\tau^{(k)}(y) - \tau^{(k-1)}(y)) + \dots \quad (28)$$

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absolute value of each term in series (28) is no greater than the corresponding term in the power series.

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{C^k l^{k-1} N^k}{\pi^k} {}_qP_B \left(\frac{2q+1}{3}; \frac{2}{3} \right) y^{\frac{2k}{3}}. \quad (29)$$

Applying the D'Alembert criterion, it follows that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{a_k}{a_{k-1}} \right| = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{Cl}{\pi} B \left(\frac{2k+1}{3}, \frac{2}{3} \right) = 0.$$

Since the series (28) converges uniformly, it follows that it also converges absolutely and uniformly.

The equation

$$u(x, y) = P(x, y) - \frac{1}{\pi} \iint_D G(x, y; \xi, \eta) f(\xi, \eta, u(\xi, \eta), u_\xi(\xi, \eta)) d\xi d\eta . \quad (33)$$

also can be solved iteratively using the method of successive approximations.

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